

The Lausiatic History

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Entry tags: Christian monasticism, Asceticism, Sayings Text (Greek: Apophthegmata), Religious Group, Text

The Lausiatic History contains descriptions of encounters and stories gleaned from others about the monks and nuns of Egypt, Syria, Asia Minor, Italy, and Palestine, as well as non-monastic ascetics from the upper classes. It was written by Palladius the bishop of Helenopolis (also known as Palladius of Galatia) around 420 C.E. It takes its modern name from the fact that it was written under the patronage of Lausus, a high-ranking administrator in the imperial court, to whom it is addressed. Palladius wrote that the stories and sayings he had collected would be edifying for all people, not only monastics, and that all readers could adapt the practices and general spiritual orientation of the monks to their own circumstances. The first 39 chapters are stories and sayings of monks and nuns, while chapters 40-70 concern the lives of venerable ascetics, men and women, from the wealthier classes.

Date Range: 419 CE - 420 CE

Region: Egyptian desert, Palestine, and Turkey

Region tags: Palestine, Turkey, Egyptian Desert

These all contained sparsely inhabited desert regions in which monasticism developed.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://monastica.ht.lu.se/>

– Source 1 Description: This is a database of manuscripts relating to early monasticism made by the University of Lund.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://portal.research.lu.se/en/equipments/monastica-a-dynamic-library-and-research-tool>

– Source 1 Description: An extensive database of texts from late antique monasticism.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: While this text was not officially funded by government mandate, the patron who personally commissioned it was a highly placed administrator to the emperor.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: While not scripture as such, it was a highly popular book among both monks and laypeople and the original Greek text was translated into many languages including Armenian, Coptic, Ethiopic and Arabic.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: Monks did not actively recruit new members. However, the text was dedicated to its wealthy patron and others in all walks of life with the hope that all could adapt the asceticism of the book's subjects to their own circumstances.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: There are multiple recensions but the differences are negligible.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The author calls his book a diegesis, a hagiographical work that avoids the use of ornate language in order to appeal to the masses.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: The whole purpose of the work is to show the ascetic lifestyles of ideal monks as examples for how to live the Christian life.

Content

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: The basis of authority in this context is the ascetic practices of early monks.

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: While there is a distinction, there is a sense in which ascetic practice through the body helps to purify the soul.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally negative

Notes: States of mind deemed negative such as restlessness or anger are attributed to demonic influence.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: Again, the relationship between body and mind/soul is not simple. The two influence each other.

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: While not described at length, there are a number of people possessed by demons who are healed by monks.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

Notes: Demons are said to have power to suggest evil thoughts to the human mind. They cannot physically manipulate people but only suggest harmful or sinful courses of action.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– I don't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– No

Notes: Demons do not punish so much as they torture people mentally and emotionally in order to divert them from the divine.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Again, demons can only act upon the mind. They have no physical efficacy.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– Yes

Notes: Monks and nuns are expected to be entirely celibate. Even married ascetics sometimes prove their worthiness through refusing sexual contact with a spouse.

↳ Adultery
– Yes

↳ Incest
– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].
– I don't know

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)
– Yes

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?
– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Notes: Manual labor is required of most monks, both for their moral edification and in order to make a living.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery is strictly forbidden, although supernatural things happen through God's agency. This indicates that "sorcery" is defined as supernatural practices not sanctioned by Christianity.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

Notes: Obedience is one of the most emphasized virtues. Elders are to be obeyed without question.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Notes: For those monks living in communities, ritual communal prayer is to be strictly observed. The Eucharist must be taken regularly, although there are no set rules in the text for how often it must be taken.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

Notes: While monks do not proselytize frequently, whenever the chance arises to put a person on the path of Christian salvation the opportunity is taken.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

Notes: Monks and non-monastic ascetics are supposed to give alms to the poor when possible.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: In general, the reward of eternal life is granted only post-mortem.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: While Christ is assumed to be in heaven, the time of his coming is unknown.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– No

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: Christ, through his death, is said to be the atoning sacrifice for the sins of the world.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: While Christianity itself has a well-defined eschatology, that is not the concern of this text.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The norms mostly concern ascetic practice, especially the avoidance of all luxury and, when possible, acts of charity.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– Yes

Notes: Norms are done in the service of the deity.

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– Only specialized religious class

Notes: While norms mostly apply to monks and nuns, they are also applied to a wealthy class of ascetics who use their wealth to benefit monks and monasteries.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

Notes: Monks are generally required to sever ties with families in order to join a new social order as a monastic.

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: Monks are expected to be loyal to their teachers/elders and to demonstrate this loyalty through unquestioning obedience.

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Notes: Ascetic discipline is the main concern of this text.

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

Notes: As an example, many monks refuse the status of ordination as bishops in order to maintain both humility and their ascetic regimens.

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Notes: While ascetic practice is certainly the main focus in this text, the principal virtue for monks is humility.

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

Notes: While contentment with physical hardship is encouraged, it is not emphasized.

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: Ascetic practice is said to confer wisdom upon the practitioner.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Notes: Bathing is considered indulgent. One monk is said to have been so virtuous that he had not taken a bath in 14 years.

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Notes: Complete celibacy is required of monks, but even married ascetics are often said to be so virtuous that they abstain from sexual relations with their spouses.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Again, total abstinence is required.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: There are various fasting regimens, but many monks eat one meal a day and abstain from luxurious foods like meat and wine.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: Meat, wine, and other luxurious foods are generally forbidden to monks.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: Many monks are said to spend long hours on their knees in prayer but this is not listed as a requirement.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Monks in communities are required to join communal prayer several times daily.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Notes: While there are no universal monastic precepts when this text was written, monks must be obedient to their superior at the monastery, must be hospitable when visitors come, and must maintain humility at all times.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 2

Notes: Communal prayer is required for those who live in large communities. For those in smaller communities or who live in solitude, each has his or her own schedule of daily prayers throughout the day.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: While in other early monastic literature monks and nuns are referred to as Father (Abba) or Mother (Amma), this language is not present in the Lausiac History.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

Drama?

– Yes

Comedy?

– No

Tragedy?

– Yes

Epic entertainment?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: There is, however, an implication that the cells of monks are holy spaces, sacralized by the mere presence of a holy man or woman.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Spiritual Elect

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Notes: While helping the needy is always encouraged, the practice is not institutionalized as such since monasticism had not yet become an officially sanctioned institution of the church.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Notes: Again, helping the needy is always encouraged but not yet institutionalized at this time in history.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: Monastic paideia or training must be gendered since monastics are segregated according to gender. However, while we know that many monasteries required that monks become literate, the Lausiac History does not emphasize this facet of monastic life.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: New monastics are given a master or teacher to train them. They must grant total obedience to this master.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

Notes: There are many sanctioned ways to support oneself or one's monastery. The only universal rule is that all must do some kind of manual labor for their living. Some make products such as woven baskets and sell them to buy food. Others grow vegetables for their own consumption.

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– Yes

↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]
– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Bibliography

General References

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